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Rural Infrastructure And The Imperatives Of Food Security In Nigeria: Issues And Institutional Challenges

Chika Bright Ezekwu, Ph.D

Department of Economics

Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Nigeria
ezekwuchika@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Among the surmountable challenges facing the 21st century Nigerian state, is the paucity or inadequacy of infrastructure especially in the rural areas. Nigeria is a low-income developing black nation where agriculture is its most significant sector. Reducing poverty, hunger, and food insecurity through adequate infrastructure are essential features of sustainable human welfare and quality of life. Finding the best solutions to provide adequate rural infrastructure and food security for Nigeria's expanding population is the foremost goal of this paper. Thus, infrastructural development and food security are twin pillars essential for sustainable progress of human life. This paper discusses the roles of infrastructure (i.e. road networks, ports and waterways, energy infrastructures, telecommunications, health facilities, education infrastructures, etc) on food security in Nigeria. It employed institutional variant of the political economy method to empirically examine the relationship between rural infrastructure and food security in Nigeria. The findings of the analysis revealed that rural infrastructural development is a necessary and a sufficient condition for the attainment of food security in Nigeria or any other nation of the world. The findings further revealed that financing rural infrastructure through adequate budgetary allocations will help provide food security for millions of Nigerians living in hunger and abject poverty. The paper recommended amongst others that federal, state, and local government should increase public-private investment in broad-based infrastructural facilities in the rural areas in order to close the infrastructural gap between the rural and urban dwellers.

Keywords: Rural, Infrastructure, Rural Infrastructure, Food, Food Security.

INTRODUCTION

The most evident display of Nigeria's underdeveloped conditions occurs in the rural areas. This can be discerned primarily from the quality of life of its population content (Ezekwu, 2005). The rural sector which harbors about 73 percent (World Bank, 1995b) of Nigeria's population is lacking in the basic infrastructural facilities required to meet the basic needs of the modern man. These basic necessities of life include food, employment and income generating opportunities, information, shelter, clothing, education, health care, and other social services to the poor (Federal Office of Statistics, 1995). Although, some features of this reality are also evident in our urban environments, a common feature of Nigeria's and Third World poverty is its concentration in the rural areas (Okowa, 1987). Todaro aptly summarized this phenomenon when he said in relation to the Third World:

Perhaps the most valid generalization about the poor is that they are disproportionately located in the rural areas...(Todaro, 198:131).

The rural population of Nigeria constitutes in the main, the Nigerian peasantry, the Nigerian poor, and the country's largest illiterate groups. It is their typology that Frantz Fanon (1968) refers to as "The Wretched of the Earth", whose endless striving for survival has not been helped by low incomes and inadequate innovations in farm practices; nor is their situation helped by the almost near absence of industrial and public sector investments in these areas. In the same vein, Olatunbosun's (1975) aptly titled "Nigeria's Neglected Rural Majority" was the first comprehensive attempt to focus attention on issue of rural neglect in Nigeria in the area of public policy. Olatunbosun argued that public policy in Nigeria has tended to favour the urban sector at the expense of the rural.

Thus, Aluko (1975) in his characteristic humour, has stated that:

All that the local areas exist for is to line up, receive and dance for state governors and commissioner, if and when they visit the local areas. But beyond this humor lies the evident fact that the rural masses have largely been viewed by their own rulers as mere objects of production meant for manipulation and exploitation; otherwise, how else can we explain the dearth of basic public utilities and social amenities in these areas (pp.7).

Given from above, a wide gap exists in the level of development of the urban and rural areas, attributable to urban bias (Okowa, 1987) in resource allocation, blamed on our colonial inheritance where all the infrastructural facilities that make life worth living were concentrated in the country's urban centers, leading to wide disparity in living standards and quality of life between the urban and rural dwellers. In the view of Olatunbosun (1975), for instance, when the British were packing for departure in 1959,

The rural areas were particularly denied social services that are essential for rural development. Modern sanitation, electricity, pipe-borne water supply, good roads, and medical services were as foreign as they were at the beginning of the colonial rule (p.18).

Apparently, Nigeria's post-independence development efforts have also not changed significantly from the colonial past. Hence, Ayinde (2021) noted that infrastructural development in Nigeria is mostly felt in the urban areas; while the rural areas suffer serious neglect. Hence, this paper investigated rural infrastructure and the imperatives of food security in Nigeria: Issues and Institutional Challenges.

The Concept of Rural Infrastructure

The word "Rural" connotes a specific geographical location on the earth surface in relation to an urban location. Spatially, rural refers to the country-side while urban refers to the city (Ezekwu, 2005:25). Hornby (2000) defined "Infrastructure" as the basic systems and services that are necessary for a country or an organization, for example buildings, transport, water and power supplies and administrative systems. On the other hand, "Rural Infrastructure" includes physical structures and services that support economic and social activities in rural areas (Vishnu, 2024). It includes the basic physical and organizational structures and facilities such as buildings, roads, power supplies, irrigation networks, extension services, warehouses, and storage facilities, etc, needed for the operation of rural society (Memon and El Bilali; 2020). Thus, adequate and well-functioning rural infrastructure can significantly improve agricultural productivity, increase income-generating opportunities and provide access to critical services like healthcare, education and clean water (Diao et al, 2024).

Idachaba (1985) in Ayinde (2021) identified three key classes of rural infrastructures in Nigeria. These classes and their components are rural physical infrastructure, rural social infrastructure, and rural institutional infrastructure.

i. Rural Physical Infrastructure

According to Idachaba, these includes transportation facilities such as government roads (federal, state and local government owned), railways, bridges, ferry services and ports; storage facilities such as silos, warehouses, cribs, and open air facilities; processing facilities such as machinery, equipment and buildings, irrigation, flood control and water resources development such as dams, irrigation and watering facilities, and drainage systems; soil conservation facilities and farm settlement electrification.

ii Rural Social Infrastructure

According to Idachaba, these include health care facilities, such as hospitals, dispensaries, maternities and health centers; education facilities such as primary and secondary schools, teacher training colleges, technical schools, vocational schools, and adult education facilities; rural utilities such as electricity and water supply.

iii. Rural Institutional Infrastructure

According to Idachaba, these are postal and telecommunication facilities such as post office, postal agencies, telephones (mobile phones). It includes financial institutions such as banks, credit societies, co-operation societies and related institutions; agricultural research facilities such as banks, credit societies, co-operation societies and related institutions; agricultural research facilities such as research sub-stations, experimental farms, and demonstration plots and, agricultural and training facilities; as well as marketing, crop and animal protection services, and farmers unions/groups, community development projects embarked upon through self-help initiatives (Ezekwu, 2005).

Nigeria's Infrastructure Index (2001-2020).

According to Ayinde (2021), Nigeria's infrastructure development using the composite Africa Infrastructure Index (AIDI) from 2001 to 2020 is shown in table 1 below. The report indicates a substantial rise in the nation's AIDI from 8.78 in 2001 to 23.27 in 2020, though this increase according to Ayinde is abysmally below the average of the top 10 countries in recent times. Out of 54 countries in Africa, Nigeria's AIDI scores fluctuate between 20.61 and 23.27, while its ranking ranged between 23rd and 24th position in recent five-year period (2016-2020). Seychelles was the top most performer with AIDI scores ranging from 94.32 in 2018 to 96.73 in 2020 (AfDB, 2020). Nigeria's AIDI scores was never in the category of top 10 between 2001-2020, while only countries like Ghana and Botswana and Cabo Verde were the only nations in the West Africa sub-region that have attained top 10 ranking in recent reports (AfDB, 2018; 2020) in Ayinde (2021).

Table 1: Nigeria’s AIDI Score 2001 – 2020

Year	AIDI Score	Year	AIDI Score
	Score/100		Score/100
2001	8.78	2011	NA
2002	9.24	2012	NA
2003	9.17	2013	17.58
2004	9.78	2014	19.35
2005	10.55	2015	20.45
2006	11.25	2016	20.60
2007	11.96	2017	21.64
2008	14.69	2018	22.37
2009	15.94	2019	22.76
2010	17.58	2020	23.27

Source: Ayinde (2021)

Nigerian Infrastructural Development Index, 2020 to 2025

It has been argued that Nigeria’s infrastructure development faces significant challenges, hindering economic growth, sustainability, and human development; with the country’s infrastructure stock estimated at only 30% of GDP, far below the 70% international benchmark set by the World Bank (Okeke et al, 2025).

Nigerian infrastructure development (2020-2025) reveals a persistent gap of over N100 billion, with a 2025 rating of 1.8/5.0 (36% score.). Although 2020 showed 107% teledensity and rapid ICT growth, the overall sector faces significant deficits. The 2021-2025 National Development Plan aims to boost this through over N348 trillion in total investments, with a strong focus on PPPs to address the deficits (Olaniwun, 2025).

Table 2: Infrastructural Development Highlights, 2020 – 2025.

2020–2023	2021–2025	2024 – 2025
The African Infrastructure Development Index (AIDI) 2020 ranked Nigeria 24 th out of 54 African countries. Despite some gains in ICT, transportation and education infrastructure often showed negative or weak contributions to growth.	2021–2025 National Development plan (NDP). The plan targets significant improvement, with a projected N348.1 trillion investment requirement, largely driven by the private.	Funding: the 2025 Federal Budget allocated N4.06 trillion (\$2.7 billion) for infrastructure. Key Projects: ongoing investment in road/highway expansion, rail, and urban development.
	Sector (N298.3 trillion).	ICT/Digital: target to improve digital financial inclusion <2% to 25% by 2025, according to a report by the development Research and Projects Centre (dRPC). Key Challenges: inadequate maintenance, funding gaps, and slow implementation of projects, which often result in a 40-50% infrastructure deficit relative to needs

Source: Olaniwun, 2025

According to Olaniwun (2025), the 2025 outlook remains focused on addressing this massive \$100 + billion deficit, with a reliance on Public Private Partnerships (PPPs) and increased budgetary allocation to boost economic growth.

The Concept of Food Security

Food is life; hence, food has become an instrument of national power (Adebayo, 2012 in Ezekwu, 2018:159). Food also is one of the basic necessities of life. It contains nutrients- substances essential for the growth, repair, and maintenance of body tissues and for the regulation of vital processes (National Geographic Education, 2024). Food security exists when all people, at all times, have physical and economic access to sufficient, safe and nutritious food that meets their dietary needs and food preference for an active and healthy life (World Food Summit, 1996 in Idisi, 2021). Similarity, FAO (2006) defined food security as a situation that exists when all people, at all times, have physical, social and economic access to sufficient, safe and nutritious food that meets their dietary needs and food preferences for an active and healthy life. Thus, the FAO identified four dimensions of food security to include: (i) Availability – National/self-sufficiency, (ii) Accessibility – Household, (iii) Utilization – Individual, and (iv) Stability – which may be considered as a time dimension that affects all the levels (FAO, 2006). Table 3 below summarizes the different dimensions of food security and their definitions.

Table 3: Dimensions of Food Security

S/N	Dimension Of Food Security	Means of Identification
1.	Physical AVAILABILITY of food	Food availability addresses the “supply side” of food security and is determine by the levels and net trade.
2.	Economic and Physical ACCESS to food	An adequate supply of food at the national or international level does not in itself guarantee household- level food security. Concerns about insufficient food access have resulted in a greater policy focus on incomes, expenditure, markets, and prices in achieving food security objectives.
3.	Food UTILIZATION	Utilization is commonly understood as the way the body makes the most of various nutrients in the food. Sufficient energy and nutrient intake by individuals are the result of good care and feeding practices, food preparation, and diversity of the diet and intra-household distribution of food. Combined with good biological utilization of food consumed, this determines the nutritional status of individuals.
4	STABILITY of the other three Dimensions over time	Even if your food intake is adequate today, you are still considered to be food insecure if you have inadequate access to food on a periodic basis, risking a deterioration of your nutritional status. Adverse weather conditions, political instability, or economic factors (unemployment, rising food prices may have an impact on your food security status)

Source: Yusuf, (2021)

Figure 1: The Food Security Framework

Source: Adedife (2001)

A perspective inferred from the above framework is the identification of the four aforementioned dimensions of food security, namely: Availability, Accessibility, Affordability, and Stability.

Food Security Challenge in Nigeria

According to UN World Food Programme (2026), a record near-35 million Nigerians are facing food insecurity, driven by conflict, climate shocks, displacement and the systemic collapse of local food systems. Escalating insurgents’ attacks are fueling the unprecedented hunger crisis, driving mass displacement, collapsing livelihoods and creating fertile ground for armed group recruitment. The World Food Programme observed that Northeast particularly Borno, Adamawa and Yobe states-remains the epicenter of the crisis, with nearly 5.8 million people facing severe food insecurity in 2026. This includes 15,000 people in Borno state who are expected to face catastrophic hunger and famine like conditions. Children and women are at greatest risk across Borno, Sokoto, Yobe and Zamfara where malnutrition rates are highest.

The challenge of food security transcends national or regional boundaries, and indeed became a global concern in 2015 when the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGS) were set (Adedipe, 2021). Goal 2 targets zero hunger by 2030, and that is, to end hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition, and promote sustainable agriculture. According to Adedipe, while the entire world is not in shortage of food, there are wide disparities in food sufficiency and food security across nations, regions and continents. Just like Nigeria, there are some areas of high incidence of food insecurity and some others with varying degrees of food security.

Table 4: Top-10 Food-Secure Countries, 2020

Global Ranking	Country	Overall Score	Affordability	Availability	Quality and Safety	Natural Resources and Resilience
1 st	Finland	85.3	90.6	82.0	93.8	73.2
2 nd	Ireland	83.8	92.2	75.7	94.0	73.2
3 rd	Netherlands	79.9	90.7	74.5	88.7	61.5
4 th	Austria	79.4	89.5	70.8	94.3	61.8
5 th	Czech Republic	78.6	86.3	70.4	87.1	70.9
6 th	United Kingdom	78.5	89.7	70.0	92.8	59.4
7 th	Sweden	78.1	89.2	65.0	92.3	67.4
8 th	Israel	78.0	89.5	75.3	93.9	46.3
9 th	Japan	77.9	90.4	73.0	83.4	58.6
10 th	Switzerland	77.7	87.9	68.4	89.6	64.2
100th	Nigeria	40.1	32.9	46.8	41.5	39.3

Source: Global Food Security Index, 2020

Table 5: Global Food Security Index, for Selected Countries, 2022

Global Ranking	Country	Overall Score	Affordability	Availability	Quality and Safety	Sustainability and Adaptation
1 st	Finland	83.7	91.9	70.5	88.4	82.6
2 nd	Ireland	81.7	92.6	70.5	86.1	75.1
3 rd	Norway	80.5	87.2	60.4	86.8	87.4
4 th	France	80.2	91.3	69.0	87.7	70.3
5 th	Netherlands	80.1	92.7	70.7	84.7	69.2
57 th	Morocco	63.0	74.5	42.9	73.1	60.0
59 th	South Africa	61.7	63.4	60.1	66.1	56.9
62 nd	Tunisia	60.3	74.5	54.1	58.8	49.7
77 th	Egypt	56.0	62.2	54.2	45.9	55.8
83 rd	Ghana	52.6	59.9	52.4	50.5	45.1
93 rd	Uganda	47.7	48.3	41.0	45.1	57.0
96 th	Cameroon	46.4	50.4	31.9	56.5	47.0
107th	Nigeria	42.0	25.0	39.5	55.6	53.7

Source: Global Food Security Index, 2022

According to Global Food Security Index (GFSI) 2025, Ghana is the most food secure country in West Africa, 7th on the continent and 83rd globally with an index score of 52.6. In the 2025 Global Hunger Index (GHI), Nigeria is ranked 115th out of 123 countries, indicating a serious and worsening food security crisis, driven by high inflation, poverty, and insecurity. Nigeria's 2025 GHI score is 32.8, a decline that highlights a severe crisis (Global Hunger Index, 2025).

Relationship between Rural Infrastructure and Food Security in Nigeria.

According to Ayide (2021), rural infrastructure development is a necessary condition for the attainment of food security of any nation of the world. It has been argued that financing rural infrastructure

(roads, crop storage equipment, provision of electricity, etc) will help provide food security for millions of people living in hunger worldwide (Uzsoki & Turley, 2019). This because improved infrastructure reduces post-harvest losses and allows farmers to access a broader market, potentially increasing their income and incentivizing higher productivity, which directly impacts food security (Isah and Ogundele, 2025). The connection between rural infrastructure and food security operates through multi-faceted pathways, including enhanced market access, income diversification, and improved nutrition. Khandker et al. (2019) studied the poverty impact of rural roads: evidence from Bangladesh. It was discovered that Kenyan households with better road access has higher dietary diversity due to increased availability of varied food products. Also, Minten et al. (2020) studied global retail chains and poor farmers: evidence from Madagascar. It was discovered that in Madagascar, improved rural roads led to greater agricultural commercialization, which strengthened household purchasing power and reduced food insecurity. In another related development, Lefe et al. (2024) carried out a study on “A vision of achieving food security: does physical infrastructure matters? A sub-Saharan African perspective. The study investigated the nexus between physical infrastructure, including transport, electricity, information and communication technology, water supply and sanitation and food security in sub-Saharan Africa. It was discovered that transport, electricity, information and telecommunication, water supply and sanitation have positive and significant effect on food security in selected SSA countries. The above is a reflection that improvement in physical infrastructure has the potential to accentuate the attainment of food security in African. Some of the key aspects of the relationship between rural infrastructure and food security include:

- (i) **Production and Productivity:** Adequate and reliable infrastructure such as irrigation and rural electrification, enables the use of modern technology leading to higher agricultural productivity and increased food sufficiency.
- (i) **Market Access and Prices:** Improved and accessible road network systems are vital for bringing farm produce to the market, which lowers transport costs and reduces food wastage, thereby ensuring stable food prices for consumers.
- (ii) **Post-Harvest Loss Reduction:** Adequate and sustainable storage facilities significantly reduced the quantity of food spoilage between harvest and consumption, there maintaining adequate quality.
- (iii) **Income and Poverty Reduction:** Functional reliable infrastructure enables farmers to connect with profitable markets, thereby increasing their income and lowering poverty levels.

Issues and institutional challenges

For any society to develop and thrive in its food security challenges, there must be on ground requisite infrastructures to aid the development of the agricultural sector. It has been argued that availability of adequate infrastructure facilities is an important prerequisite for sustainable food security. Thus, food security depends on good infrastructural facilities and is an instrument to improve the economy (Adama et al., 2022). It has seen observed cost of food production which will ensure food security (Oyewole and Oloko, 2006).

However, the state of Nigeria’s rural infrastructures poses a great challenge to food security. The challenge of bad roads, poor health systems, poor education infrastructure, poor (or zero) electricity supply, etc overtime have made it difficult for Nigeria to achieve adequate food security. Though successive governments in Nigeria initiated several projects and programmes to improve the quality and quantity of infrastructure in the rural areas, yet the impact of such projects and programmes on the lives of many rural people in Nigeria is still limited. This is because the projects and programmes could not be sustained for a long period of time due to lack of political will and commitment; and inadequate involvement of the beneficiaries of these projects and programmes (Ezekwu, 2005: 6).

The feeling that successive governments have neglected us became transformed into an attitude of “What can we do for ourselves”. Because of their concern (i.e. the rural people) mostly for education, health, access roads, etc., embarked on a number of self-help projects (Ezekwu, 2005: 6-7). Thus, self-help projects became popular among rural communities in Nigeria. By this approach, rural people are involved in initiating discussions on projects as well as the approval of projects.

The Challenges of Food Security

According to Liman (2021), the following are some of the key institutional or developmental challenges facing the agricultural sector, food security, and indeed the farmer today.

- i. Inconsistent agricultural policies and poor coordination.
- ii. Shortage of reliable planning statistics.
- iii. Decaying and inadequate infrastructure for research.
- iv. Low mechanization, inappropriate technology.
- v. Poor rural infrastructures- power, roads and water supply etc.
- vi. Poor credit- access and management.
- vii. Storage and preservation – poorly developed.
- viii. Weak private sector linkage-need to encourage private sector collaboration.
- ix. Extension – poorly resourced, low staff morale and inadequacy.
- x. Crop, livestock and fishery – poor quality feeds and diseases (pp 82).

Given from above, Nigeria is yet to achieve food self-sufficiency and food security. It has been observed that Nigeria spends US\$5.0 billion on food import annually; and Nigeria's agriculture is till at substance level, with low productivity and poor return on investment (Oyeleke, 2021).

CONCLUSION

The rural areas still remain the food basket of Nigeria and the fulcrum of agricultural and economic development of the country. Hence, rural infrastructure, that is, feeder roads, electricity supply, storage facilities water supply, storage facilities, water supply and sanitation has been found as a critical drive of food security. Improved infrastructure enhances food production and national output by facilitating input access, reduction in post- harvest losses through better storage, low transportation cost, and connecting farmers to the market, thus ultimately stabilizing prices and improving living standards.

It has been argued that lack of adequate infrastructure leads to high post-harvest losses, market isolation for farmers, and insecurity especially in area with poor transportation and ICT facilities.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the outcome of this paper, the following recommendations were made:

- (i) Government at all levels should as a matter of urgency provide broad- based infrastructural facilities such as good access roads, electricity, water supply, sanitation, storage and market facilities, school, etc for rural dwellers to enhance adequate food production and sufficiency for the nation.
- (ii) Government at all levels should build and improve access to information and communication technology in the rural areas.
- (iii) Governments at all levels should build schools for rural communities aimed at teaching agricultural practices as part of its curriculum
- (iv) Government at all levels should revive adult literacy and extension programmes for rural people, especially for rural women.
- (v) The urban bias paradox of resource allocation in Nigeria should be dethroned.

Government should develop the rural areas hand in glove with their urban counterpart. This will give rise to all- round development of the country thereby reducing insecurity in the rural areas.

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